

CAA Netherland-Flanders National Chapter Information and Report

National Chapter*: Netherland-Flanders

Submitted by*: Ronald Visser, Devi Taelman, Alex Brandsen and Alicia Walsh

Date Submitted*: 14 maart 2024

Please complete the following information about your national chapter. The information in fields with asterisks () will be published on the CAA International website. All other information will not be publicly shared. Reports should be emailed to CAA's Secretary at secretary@caa-international.org.*

Chapter Organisational Details

Chapter Leadership

Term Dates for the Current Steering Committee:

Name*	Chapter Position*	Email Address
Ronald Visser	Chair	r.m.visser@saxion.nl
Devi Taelman	Treasurer	devi.taelman@vub.be
Alex Brandsen	Communications officer	a.brandsen@arch.leidenuniv.nl
Alicia Walsh	Secretary	aliciascw@gmail.com

All National Chapters must have at least three officers according to CAA's Constitution. Any time there is a change in your chapter's leadership, please notify the CAA Secretary.

CAA Steering Committee Representative*: Ronald Visser

This is often the chair, but any member of the chapter's leadership can be designated as the Steering Committee representative. However, the Steering Committee representative **must be a member of CAA International** while serving in this capacity.

Chapter Membership

Total Number of Current Members: 154

If you have different categories membership categories for Full Members, Students, and/or Low Income Members, please provide the numbers of members at each level:

Membership Level	Number of Members
No levels, because membership is free	154

Chapter Contact Information

Chapter Website*: <https://nlfl.caa-international.org/>

Chapter Social Media Channel(s) (optional):

Platform*	Handle*
Twitter (X)	https://twitter.com/caanlfl
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/caanlfl/
Instagram	-
LinkedIn	-
YouTube	-
Mastodon	https://akademienl.social/@caanlfl

General Contact Email for the Chapter*:

info@caanlfl.nl

If you do not have a general chapter email address, please contact the secretary to have one created. The email can be set up as a separate inbox or as a forwarding account.

Chapter Description

Brief Description of Your Chapter*:

Please provide a few sentences or a paragraph describing your chapter, such as the kinds of activities you organise, when it was founded, who should join, etc. These descriptions should not include specific details about upcoming activities as they are meant to be “evergreen” and to drive traffic to your chapter’s website to learn more.

CAA Netherlands – Flanders (CAA-NL-FL) represents the Dutch and Flemish national chapters of the international CAA. The aims of the CAA-NL-FL are to bring together archaeologists, mathematicians and computer scientists based in the Netherlands and Flanders. In addition we encourage communication between these disciplines and to give a survey of present work in the field. During our yearly meetings we stimulate discussion and future progress. The CAA-NL was founded on 26 september 1996. CAA-NL became CAA-NL-FL in 2010 as a joint chapter for the Netherlands and Flanders, because we share the same language. It has been a growing community ever since. We organize an annual Chapter Meeting and every two years this is a joint-chapter meeting with our German neighbours (CAA-DE). It is our aim to encourage both established and early career researchers to participate in our meetings.

Our organisation is currently administered by four speakers: Ronald Visser, Alicia Walsh, Devi Taelman, and Alex Brandsen. Membership of CAA-NL-FL shall be open to anyone without payment. Anyone attending a meeting of CAA-NL-FL will automatically be a member.

Translated Description in Your Chapter’s Language(s)*:

If you would like to include the same description in your chapter’s language(s) as well, please provide the translation.

Report for the CAA National Chapter of Australasia

Reporting Period*: 2023

Netherland-Flanders Update on the National Chapter Activities:* *(Please insert additional pages, if needed)*

In April 2023, we acted as the host chapter for the international CAA conference in Amsterdam (<https://2023.caaconference.org/>). This was our main meeting and because of this big event, we dedicated our time to organizing this and this event also served as our local chapter meeting. Several members of CAA-NL-FL contributed by organizing sessions or presentations during the conference. In addition, several members participated during the post-conference excursions.

During the national archaeology conference of the Netherlands, de Reuvsdagen (November 2023), several members of CAA-NL presented their work on diverse topics, ranging from Agent-Based Modelling to text mining.

Following the CAA International conference in Amsterdam, Jitte Waagen resigned from the CAA-NL-FL Steering Committee. From several candidates, Alicia Walsh was elected during our annual General Meeting, as Jitte's replacement.

In November CAA-NL-FL and CAA-DE organized an online workshop and day of lectures on Agent-Based Modelling in which 40 people participated (76 registered).

The cooperation with the Digital Archaeology Group has intensified

Updates for CAA's ESC

Is there any information about your chapter or its activities that you would like to tell CAA's Executive Steering Committee? This information will only be shared with the CAA's officers and will not be made publicly available.